

2019

**IC
DSST**

EmC-ICDSST 2019

Madeira, Portugal
May 27th – 29th, 2019

EmC-ICDSST 2019

**5th International Conference on Decision
Support System Technology – ICDSST 2019
& EURO Mini Conference 2019
on “Decision Support Systems: Main
Developments & Future Trends”**

University of Madeira, Portugal, 27th-29th May 2019

**Editors: P. S. Abreu Freitas, F. Dargam, R., Ribeiro, J. M.
Moreno Jimenez, J. Papathanasiou**

ISBN: 978-989-8805-44-7

DSS

DECISION SUPPORT
SYSTEMS

Collaborative value modelling in widely participated decision support processes

Carlos A. Bana e Costa, Ana C.L. Vieira, Mónica D. Oliveira

CEG-IST, Centre for Management Studies of Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Av. Rovisco Pais, 1049-001 Lisboa, Portugal
carlosbana@tecnico.ulisboa.pt, monica.oliveira@tecnico.ulisboa.pt,
ana.lopes.vieira@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

João Bana e Costa

Decision Eyes, Rua da Prata, 80, Lisboa, Portugal
joao.bana@decisioneyes.com

ABSTRACT

Departing from the classical collaborative knowledge acquisition methodology in expert systems literature, the ‘collaborative value modelling’ framework was developed. It combines two decision support processes: Web-Delphi to elicit individual judgemental knowledge from a (very) large number of stakeholders, and Decision Conferencing (DC) in which the knowledge acquired is then digested by a small group of key-players, to collaboratively develop a widely informed multicriteria value model. This new socio-technical framework was already tested in real complex evaluation contexts, supported by the Welphi platform and the MACBETH method. This paper focuses on the Welphi process for weighting population-health objectives that informed a subsequent multicriteria DC to construct a European Population Health Index under the EURO-HEALTHY H2020 project. It shows that enhancing MACBETH decision conferencing with an ex ante Web-Delphi process fostered higher participation and collaboration in multicriteria modelling. Furthermore, it shows how the Welphi platform, by collecting participants’ changes of opinion (or judgements) between Delphi rounds, provides a mean to understand the knowledge construction process itself. Current research under the IMPACT HTA H2020 and MEDI-VALUE FCT projects addresses both technical and social challenges, on the one hand, to find ways for improving the platform in order to understand the reasons behind opinion changes and knowledge generated by participants’ interactions and comments, and on the other hand, to explore behavioral aspects within and across Delphi, DC and MACBETH web-based group decision support systems.

Keywords: Collaborative modelling; Knowledge acquisition; Multicriteria decision conferencing; Participatory process; MACBETH; Web-Delphi; WELPHI

INTRODUCTION

Delphi and decision conferencing (DC) can be appropriately viewed as group decision support systems (DSS) [1], as they both make use of an information basis and decision support methods and technology to acquire individual knowledge and stimulate collaborative group agreement. From the social view point, the difference between these two particular DSS is that Delphi are non-face-to-face anonymous processes able to involve a large number of participants, whereas DC develops on open face-to-face settings restricted to relatively small groups. From the technical perspective, we will restrict the discussion of their use on decision aiding contexts which ultimate objective is the construction of multicriteria evaluation models

under the working hypotheses of multi-attribute additive value modelling (MAVM) [2] and using the MACBETH approach [3, 4]. Specifically, we will mention the enchainment use of the Welphi platform [5] and the M-MACBETH software [6] to develop, respectively, Web-Delphi and DC processes, framed on the recently proposed ‘collaborative value modelling framework’ [7]. The next section is devoted to this novel socio-technical framework, followed by the description of its application to a real case of weighting population health objectives in Europe.

THE COLLABORATIVE VALUE MODELLING FRAMEWORK

The expert systems literature has recognized the value of including a large number of experts to help dealing with the increase complexity of current applications [8]. Collecting information from multiple sources (experts) has numerous benefits, such as an improved knowledge of the problem domain, and enhanced “knowledge base validity, consistency, completeness, accuracy, and relevancy,” that will produce better results within multidimensional problems [9]. Wagner [10] in a recent review over the last Thirty Years of Expert System Case Studies identified different hybrid knowledge-based systems that combine multiple knowledge sources to develop expert systems that are currently exploring how different methodologies can be combined to face this challenge. However, the development of a collaborative knowledge acquisition process raises several challenges, particularly on how to use technological platforms to assist knowledge acquisition tasks that involve a large number of experts and stakeholders that can be geographically dispersed.

Drawing from the collaborative knowledge acquisition literature and from the idea that “it is possible to realize MAVM processes in which integration and interaction are at different levels” [11], we designed the above referred collaborative value modelling framework, a new socio-technical framework that departs from Web-Delphi processes to elicit and analyse individual judgemental knowledge from a (very) large and diverse number of stakeholders; the knowledge thus acquired is then digested by a small group of key-players, in a subsequent DC process, to collaboratively develop a widely informed multicriteria evaluation model.

A detailed description of the different stages of the Collaborative Value Modelling framework can be found in [7]. In this paper we focus on describing how the knowledge acquired flows between the two decision support processes used as environment components of the framework: Welphi and Decision conferencing (DC). Quoting Vieira et al. (2019) [7]: “At the heart [of the collaborative value modelling framework] are the multiple stakeholders whose involvement takes place in two different environments, assisted by the facilitation team: a participatory environment in the form of a non-face-to-face Web-Delphi, with a large number of participants; and a collaborative environment in the form of a face-to-face multicriteria decision conferencing, with a group of key-players.”

Welphi was developed using the Microsoft ASP.Net framework supported by an SQL Server database. The front-end makes extensive use of JQuery and Ajax to provide an easy experience for the users. Welphi has three main sections of interaction. The first section is where the user sets up the process itself. This includes the definition of the indicators under study, the answer scale to be used throughout the process rounds and the addition of the participants e-mails. The second section lets the user setup, monitor and analyse each round. It is possible to edit invitation and reminder e-mails’ bodies, start and stop the round as well access the participants answering status and the round statistics. Welphi also integrates the novel online MACBETH-based decision support system that also implements the MACBETH approach in a web setting environment [5].

A PROCESS OF COLLABORATIVE VALUE MODELLING FOR WEIGHTING

The EURO-HEALTHY case

The collaborative value modelling framework has been fully applied for developing a MAVM Population Health Index (PHI) model, under the EURO-HEALTHY H2020 project, to appraise PH across 269 European regions. Three separate Web-Delphi processes took place, always using the Welphi platform. Based on scientific information, the first one enabled to build a population-health value tree with 10 areas of concern, each one of them clustering multiple indicators. They operationalize a total of 42 population health objectives, which weighting process started with the second Web-Delphi. Finally, the shapes of the respective value-functions were the object of the third Web-Delphi. Given the multidimensional nature of the PH concept, many geographically dispersed experts and stakeholders from different areas were involved. Those three types of shared judgmental knowledge, thus collected, were analyzed and discussed by a group of 13 key-players, each type during a one-day decision conference to achieve agreement on, respectively, the PHI value-tree, the final weights of the objectives and the respective value functions. This paper focuses only on the weighting collaborative modelling activities, to illustrate how weighting judgements were friendly and comprehensively elicited from a large and diverse number of participants and how the weighting knowledge collected with Welphi informed the weighting decision conference.

Web-Delphi for weighting

The Web-Delphi for weighting was a one-month process that took place between February 29 and April 4, 2016. In three rounds, qualitative weighting judgements on the indicators that operationalize European health objectives were collected from 61 participants. The knowledge elicitation phase started with the design of the questionnaire of the first round of the Web-Delphi process (Figure 8). In weighting, it was important to consider that, technically, in an additive value model, each weight is a quantitative measure of the relative importance of swinging between lower and upper performance levels on the respective indicator. In the case, weighting judgements were elicited by asking the participants to answer to the question: “To reduce health inequalities in Europe, how important is to close this gap?” All gaps were shown on the Welphi platform and defined between the worst and the best performance levels on the respective indicator, across all European regions. In the beginning of the first Delphi round, participants accessed the list of indicators and the respective gaps and gave their individual qualitative weighting judgements by choosing one of the six MACBETH categories, from very weak to extreme, directly on the platform, while considering “how big is the gap and how important it is to develop policies to close the gap in view of reducing health inequalities in Europe” [12].

Figure 8: Web-Delphi for weighting in each area of concern: answers in the first round [12].

In the beginning of the second Delphi round, participants were presented with an anonymous summary of all participants' answers. It is this iterative nature of the Delphi method that enables the knowledge analysis phase of the collaborative value modelling framework. On the one hand, quantitative feedback was given in a table with each row indicating the percentage (and number) of participants' weighting judgements on each qualitative MACBETH category. It is important to mention that no statistical aggregation measure was delivered. This strategy, like a voting process as the one adopted in the [13] study, was more adequate to promote reflection. This was enhanced, on the other hand, by qualitative feedback in the form of comments that participants could give to justify their judgements. At the light of the feedback information provided, in round 2 participants were invited to confirm or revise their previous judgements. A similar process took place in a third and final round.

Individual opinion changes were used as measures of the usefulness of the Delphi method for collecting weights information. There were indicators where there was more individual opinion change on both rounds than in other indicators. The indicators with less opinion change, either started with agreement from the first round or no group majority was reached; whereas the indicators with more individual opinion changes reached a group majority judgement on round 2.

At the end, majority rules were applied to the final distributions of weighting judgements, in order to identify the indicators for which group majority judgements existed and those ones with controversy results.

Multicriteria decision conferencing for weighting

The one-day weighting decision conference took place, in Lisbon, on October 25, 2016, attended by 13 experts who had also participated in the preceding weighting Web-Delphi. Departing from the analysis and discussion of the qualitative weighting knowledge there acquired, the group developed the weighting model activities depicted in Figure 2 and moved forward the value modelling process by achieving an agreement on numerical weights to the indicators' gaps, with the support of M-MACBETH. When Delphi majority qualitative weighting judgements were not respected by the final quantitative weights agreed in the DC,

clear justifications were asked in order to guarantee the transparency of the whole collaborative value modelling process developed. Within the DC process, participants later verified and validated the weights of the PHI model.

Figure 9: Flowchart of the weighting decision conference activities [14].

CONCLUSIONS

The Web-Delphi, as used in stage 2 of the collaborative value modelling framework, showed to be effective in “introducing knowledge acquisition as a cognitive process” [15]. This is in line with the state-of-the-art of knowledge acquisition. Furthermore, the way in which the Web-Delphi was designed allowed to capture disagreements among participants, while witnessing their evolution towards agreement – a feature usually only captured during face-to-face processes [16]). The process was also an efficient way to operationalise knowledge acquisition from 61 geographically dispersed participants, as it allowed for an automatic record of the information collected which saved facilitation time and avoided unnecessary errors, simultaneously making the information collected available for the subsequent stages of the process. Finally, having available previous knowledge information proved to increase the confidence of the DC group in developing their tasks while reducing the time generally allocated to them.

Analysis of data stability and individual opinion change are key aspects to understand participatory processes, particularly the Delphi method. Further technical research within the IMPACT HTA H2020 is now being conducted to explore the reasons behind opinion changes and the insights provided by Delphi participants’ comments along the process. Further social research within the MEDI-VALUE FCT is being conducted to capture behavioural aspects that may occur within Delphi processes and that may be relevant to DC participants interpreting and understanding Delphi results. Both projects also address other socio-technical issues within and across Delphi, DC and MACBETH web-based group decision support systems.

REFERENCES

- [1] DeSanctis, G. and R.B. Gallupe, *A Foundation for the Study of Group Decision Support Systems*. Management Science, 1987. **33**(5): p. 589-609.
- [2] Winterfeldt, D.v. and W. Edwards, *Decision Analysis and Behavioral Research*. 1986: Cambridge University Press. 626.
- [3] Bana e Costa, C.A., J.-M. De Corte, and J.-C. Vansnick, *Macbeth*. International Journal of Information Technology & Decision Making, 2012. **11**(02): p. 359-387.
- [4] Bana e Costa, C.A. and J.-C. Vansnick, *MACBETH — An interactive path towards the construction of cardinal value functions*. International Transactions in Operational Research, 1994. **1**(4): p. 489-500.
- [5] Welphi. *Welphi*. 2017; Available from: <http://www.welphi.com/>.
- [6] M-MACBETH . *M-MACBETH*. 2017; Available from: <http://m-macbeth.com/>.
- [7] Vieira, A.C.L., M.D. Oliveira, and C.A. Bana e Costa, *Enhancing knowledge construction processes within multicriteria decision analysis: The Collaborative Value Modelling framework*. Omega, 2019.
- [8] Wagner, W.P., M.K. Najdawi, and Q.b. Chung, *Selection of knowledge acquisition techniques based upon the problem domain characteristics of production and operations management expert systems*. Expert Systems, 2001. **18**(2): p. 76-87.
- [9] Medsker, L., M. Tan, and E. Turban, *Knowledge acquisition from multiple experts: Problems and issues*. Expert Systems with Applications, 1995. **9**(1): p. 35-40.
- [10] Wagner, W.P., *Trends in expert system development: A longitudinal content analysis of over thirty years of expert system case studies*. Expert Systems with Applications, 2017. **76**: p. 85-96.
- [11] Marttunen, M., et al., *How to design and realize participation of stakeholders in MCDA processes? A framework for selecting an appropriate approach*. EURO Journal on Decision Processes, 2015. **3**(1-2): p. 187-214.
- [12] EURO-HEALTHY WP6, *Technical report on scenario building and analysis of policies*. 2017: Instituto Superior Técnico - Universidade de Lisboa. p. 197.
- [13] Bana E Costa, C.A., et al., *A socio-technical approach for group decision support in public strategic planning: the Pernambuco PPA case*. Group Decision and Negotiation, 2014. **23**(1): p. 5-29.
- [14] EURO-HEALTHY WP6, *Development of the multicriteria model to evaluate Population Health*. 2016: Instituto Superior Técnico - Universidade de Lisboa. p. 168.
- [15] Cairó, O., *KAMET: A comprehensive methodology for knowledge acquisition from multiple knowledge sources*. Expert Systems with Applications, 1998. **14**(1): p. 1-16.
- [16] Vivacqua, A.S., A.C.B. Garcia, and A. Gomes, *BOO: Behavior-oriented ontology to describe participant dynamics in collocated design meetings*. Expert Systems with Applications, 2011. **38**(2): p. 1139-1147.